

INCLUDING DIGITAL AWARENESS AS A COMPETENCE IN A NETWORK ENGINEERING DEGREE

R. Vidal¹

Department of Network Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Castelldefels, Spain
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2217-029X>

J. Alcober

Department of Network Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Castelldefels, Spain
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9543-472X>

C. Cervelló-Pastor

Department of Network Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Castelldefels, Spain
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8056-0774>

E. Garcia-Villegas

Department of Network Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Castelldefels, Spain
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6005-9608>

J. M. Yúfera

Department of Network Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)
Castelldefels, Spain
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9748-0490>

Conference Key Areas: *Attractiveness of Engineering i Engineering Skills*

Keywords: *digital awareness, network engineering, degree competences, attractiveness of engineering, social impact of engineering*

¹ rafael.vidal@entel.upc.edu

ABSTRACT

Information and communications technology (ICT) engineers play a key part in our society's digitization process. To foster that role, the Castelldefels School of Telecommunications and Aerospace Engineering (EETAC) of UPC's Degree in Network Engineering currently includes a new competence termed digital awareness. This report demonstrates the initiative's first outcomes, including the teaching resources created, and feedback from students and teachers. In addition, the findings of a high school poll are presented, indicating a high level of interest in this new competence.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

The digitization of our society is most likely the first technology transformation that can be termed universal and essential. In this era, controlling individuals' data, the digital gap, fake news, algorithm bias, and cybercrime are all key issues that society, governments, and corporations are dealing with at the moment. Engineers in ICT play a vital role in this challenge. To overcome this, we feel it is critical to introduce a new competence known as digital awareness into their education. Its goal is to analyse both the positive and negative elements of a certain technology or technical solution, and to provide guidelines not only for its design, which should adhere to digital awareness guidelines, but also for its righteous use.

Digital awareness relates various topics linked to the safe and responsible use of technology, which we categorise as follows [1]: digital wellness, cybersecurity, reliable information, digital identity, online education, digital parenting, digital inclusion, digital development, data protection, and digital citizenship. Some of them can also be found in the new release of the European Digital Competence Framework for citizens [2]. Currently, we are incorporating digital awareness competence into the Castelldefels School of Telecommunications and Aerospace Engineering (EETAC) at UPC's Degree in Network Engineering following the plan presented in [1]. Note that the number of girls enrolled in this degree is below 20% [3].

1.2 Motivation

This paper aims to show the initial results of this initiative. The educational materials designed and their level of success, are determined by conducting a poll research and comparing the results to instructor evaluations.

One additional reason for building this ability is to investigate the impact of technology on society, thereby providing a social viewpoint to engineering courses, which is often lacking. This new perspective has the potential to increase the number of girls pursuing technical education [4][5]. Then, we provide the preliminary results of a poll conducted in high schools to determine whether acquiring this new ability could increase the attraction of this degree, with a special focus on the interests of female students.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Introduction of the competence in the degree

Five topics related to digital awareness have been introduced this academic year. Taking Bloom's taxonomy [6] as reference, the competence is presented in "Business Management" (1st course) and understood in "Internet Architecture and Protocols" (2nd course); the upper levels of the taxonomy are worked in "Mobility Networks and Services", "Applications Engineering", "Network Security" (3rd course) and, in the future, in the bachelor thesis (see the syllabus here [7]).

To work the competency, audiovisual content is used, typically one video for each subject. Teachers offer a description of the video material and supervise the script, which is generated by a specialised firm, as well as the production, which is handled by the campus's audiovisual services. A single video [8] was created and tested during the first semester test this approach. Teachers used it in the project-based course "Applications Engineering" to convey the notion of digital awareness in the context of their subject matter, so that students may incorporate it into the design, execution, and presentation of their project. The competence is addressed similarly to any other evaluable part of the project. In other words, its progress is reported on in follow-up meetings, and its execution is evaluated in the project presentation. In other disciplines, the videos created will be used to develop H5P-based interactive elements that will aid in the competence evaluation.

2.2 Poll-based study

A survey was carried out at the end of the first semester to assess the introduction of the competence in the "Applications Engineering" subject from the student's perspective. Its findings are compared to the data provided by the teachers. During the second semester, a more comprehensive investigation was conducted among students from three high schools: two in the province of Barcelona, and one in the province of Tarragona. We asked 26 questions in four blocks concerning the film itself, its content, as well as their interest in studying engineering and, in particular, ICT, and the viability and relevance of adding social impact concepts such as digital awareness in their studies.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Undergraduate students

All 17 enrolled students responded to the survey by offering examples of their digital awareness projects. However, some of the responses show a superficial or possibly incomplete attainment of the competence. The feedback supplied by teachers reinforced this perception. Better results are expected when students have worked on this competence in multiple disciplines. A whopping 94.1% believe they will use this skill in their careers. Concerning the film itself, teachers have used it as a classroom material, and 94.1% of students agree it is beneficial for presenting digital awareness content.

3.2 Secondary school students

We received 221 responses, with 46.6% male (blue), 48.9% female (red), and 4.5% undefined. The distribution of courses is as follows: 27.5% from the first compulsory secondary education course (12 years old), 5% from the second, 30.6% from the third, 21.2% from junior high-school, and 15.8% senior high-school. Regarding the response values, 5 signifies "strongly agree" and 1 means "strongly disagree."

Figure 1 illustrates that the concept of digital awareness is relevant to most people ($98.2\% \geq 3$). The average values, shown by dashed lines reveal only minor variances across genders. When asked if app developers should follow digital awareness guidelines, students responded in a similar way". Fig. 2 shows a poor interest in following engineering studies, particularly among females: 18.45% more girls are not interested (answers ≤ 2) in these degrees, while 15.03% more boys are (answers ≥ 4). Respondents' interest in a subset of engineering degrees, namely the ICT area, deteriorates slightly, as expected: 48.4% rate it as 1, and 19.6% rate it as 2, showing similar gender disparity.

When it comes to the appeal of including the social impact of engineering and digital awareness in engineering or ICT degrees, respectively (see Fig. 3), the global responses are quite balanced. Looking into the level of studies and gender, senior high-school students show the highest interest, with girls having higher average values than boys: 3.71 vs 2.83 for adding the social impact of engineering, and 3.73 vs 3.16 for digital awareness inclusion in ICT degrees. This is also noteworthy given the poor interest in engineering and ICT degrees, with average values of 2.33 and 1.85.

Fig. 1. Importance of digital awareness

Fig. 2. Interest in follow a engineering degree

Fig. 3. Attractiveness of social impact of engineering (a) generic (b) digital awareness in ICT degrees

Both studies show the interest in the digital awareness concept. For undergraduate students, its incorporation as a competence will demonstrate if, as in the situations discussed in [5], more EETAC girl students pick the Degree in Network Engineering at the end of the common courses. Concerning secondary school, our aim is to conduct studies related to talks and experimental activities similar to [4] but focused on digital awareness, to better know its capacity to attract girls to ICT degrees.

4 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by the teaching innovation project "Introduction of the competence of digital awareness in the degree of Degree in Telematics Engineering", ICE-UPC 2021. The authors would like to express their gratitude to the "Applications Engineering" teachers and students, as well as the teachers and support personnel who made the high school survey possible.

REFERENCES

- [1] Vidal, R., Alcober, J., Cervelló-Pastor, C., Garcia-Villegas, E., & Yúfera, J.M. (2021), Creating digital awareness, Proceedings of XV Jornadas de Ingeniería Telemática (JITEL), Universidad de A Coruña, A Coruña 2021, pp. 105-111.
- [2] The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp), European Commission, EU Science Hub, URL: https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/digcomp_en (last visited: 19th April 2022).
- [3] Bachelor's Degree in Telematics Engineering (UPC) EETAC, Estudis Universitaris de Catalunya (see "Admissions and enrollement), URL: <https://estudis.aqu.cat/euc/en/Titulacions/Fitxa?titulacioid=9531#> (last visited: 19th April 2022).
- [4] Nietner, L. F., & Wallace, D. R. (2017), The Social Impact of STEM, Experienced: Studies With an Engineering Design Concept for Smart Devices. Proceedings of International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, vol. 58158, p. V003T04A020.
- [5] Nilsson, L. (2015), New York Times, How to Attract Female Engineers, URL: <https://www.nytimes.com/2015/04/27/opinion/how-to-attract-female-engineers.html> (last visited: 19th April 2022).
- [6] Huit, W. (2011), Bloom et al.'s taxonomy of the cognitive domain, Educational psychology interactive, 22.
- [7] Bachelor's degree in Network Engineering, EETAC, URL <https://eetac.upc.edu/en/study/bachelors-deegrees/telematics-engineering-1>
- [8] Digital Awareness: Applications and Social Networking (subtitled video), Click & Safe, Zonavideo UPC, URL: <https://zonavideo.upc.edu/video/61f8f58d02108056db0b2382> (last visited: 19th April 2022).